

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Sustainable farming techniques and renewable fertilisers to combine agriculture, water and environment

SOS_AQUA aims to advance and promote sustainable agricultural techniques associated with the use of "renewable" fertilisers that come from slurry and digestate treatment. The goal is to improve efficiency of existing nutrients on farms while reducing reliance on synthetic mineral fertilisers.

Challenge

Develop a system to increase the use of the liquid fraction of digestate (the most present and most problematic fraction to be valorised) by mixing it with water in fertigation for efficient use of nutrients and to save mineral fertiliser input.

Activity

Three innovative agricultural systems were evaluated and compared with agronomic trials from a conventional agricultural system: traditional soil management, chemical fertiliser input, conventional application and sprinkler irrigation.

Results

Three agrosystems were successful:

1. Non-tillage based on spring-summer crops (sorgum and maize) alternating with autumn-winter cover crops, fertigated with ammonium sulphate from stripping treatment of digestate, injected through drip lines in sub-irrigation.
2. Minimal tillage based on double crops, the first for food and the other for biogas, fertigated with microfiltered digestate injected through drip lines in sub-irrigation.
3. Conventional for food and non-food but fertigated with microfiltered digestate spread through a rainger irrigator.

Fertigation with microfiltered digestate in subsurface drip line

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